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HISTORY OF PUBLICATION OF THE NEWSPAPER “QAZAQ TILI” AND ITS STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Since the independence of our country, it has become possible to write the history of the Kazakh people from a new perspective. It is going to be today's demand. Today it is necessary to reflect on the past and open the "blank" pages where the truth is not told. At the same time, the First President of the Republic of Kazakhstan Nursultan Abishevich Nazarbayev in his article among the program "A Look Into The Future: Modernization of Public Consciousness" said: "I want my nation to take every step firmly and confidently into the future, making the rich history and ancient national traditions a solid foundation for future prosperity" (Nazarbayev, 2017). It is known that plenty research has been conducted in various fields of history of Kazakhstan, including many works on the history of the Kazakh press. However, it is important to determine the impact of the Kazakh press on the political, social, economic and cultural development of the country for more than a century, to determine its place in the development of society on the basis of the requirements of historical science. Nevertheless some works have been prepared in the domestic historical science in the context of this requirement, a lot of work has been done to determine the past of the Kazakh press, and so it is clear that today the past of this edition has not been fully researched yet as a whole study. Therefore, it is necessary to study the Kazakh press, including regional periodicals, and determine its past activities. Although a number of textbooks, manuals, and research papers on the history of the establishment and development of the Kazakh press and its development have been written since our independence from 1991, and still we cannot say that the history of the press has been fully studied. In this regard, it is time to study and analyze the role of the former "Qazaq Tili" newspaper, which has been raising the issue of the Semipalatinsk region at various stages since the beginning of the twentieth century, and the current time it's "Semey Tany" newspaper. Exactly a century ago, the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was published on the 4th of

December, 1919. In particular, it is important to pass on to today's generation the history and work of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", which is should be considered as the foundation of the Soviet Kazakh press, and it marked the 100th anniversary of its edition last year. In general, the "Qazaq Tili" newspaper has changed its name several times in its history due to socio-political changes in the country. The edition under the name "Qazaq Tili" was published on the 4th of December, 1919, then it changed names, such as "Zhana Auyl", "Qyzyl Dala", "Socialdy Shygys", "Ekpindi", "Semey Pravdasy", "Ertis", but the last changed name the "Semey Tany" was from 1965.

KEYWORDS: Print, History, Society, Politics, Press, Personality, Newspaper, Culture, Region, Nation, Intelligentsia.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is known that in the second decade of the XX century, Kazakhstan first formed as an autonomous structure of the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic and then the USSR, so publicizing the development of the country in the conditions of socialist doctrine and focusing on the press to mobilize them to meet these requirements. In order to fulfill this requirement, in 1919, the Soviet newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was published in the East Kazakhstan region of that time. The first organizers of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" were Kazakh intellectuals such as M. Turganbayev, M. Aueyev, Zh. Aimauytov, Sh. Tokzhigitov, S. Donentaev, and such figures as Sh. Musataiuly, Sh. Kudaiberdiuly, S. Yesova, and M. Dulatov contributed to the publication of articles with a weighty content. In general, during this period in Semipalatinsk, along with the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", the newspaper "Saryarka" was published and operated as a propagandist of Soviet doctrine and was the press organ of the Alash Center in the region. It is known that the newspaper published articles by the leaders of the Alash movement and raised issues of national interest. The works of Alash activists of Semey region were published in the newspapers.

The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" has been published since the 4th of December, 1919 to the present day. Today's name of the edition is "Semey Tany". This is because in the first years the newspaper was published under the name "Qazaq Tili", in the following years - "Zhana Auyl", "Qyzyl Dala", "Socialdy Shygys", "Ekpindi", "Semey Pravdasy", "Ertis", and for the last 53 years it is called "Semey Tany". In the textbook, we focus on the history of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", which was published through the first 20 years of Soviet power, and the spiritual values of today's generation. Because, the activities of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", which followed the publications "Saryarka" and "Abai", published in Semipalatinsk, which was a socio-political environment for Kazakh intellectuals, differed from the contradictions of the first years of Soviet rule. The events in the society in this direction are widely covered in the current newspaper. Therefore, it is important to give impetus to the minds of young people about the future of the country through the work of the Soviet newspaper "Qazaq Tili", which was published in the Semipalatinsk region in the early twentieth century and spread to the whole Kazakh land. And due to the need to achieve this goal, special attention was paid to the transmission of the role of the newspaper to today's generation, which has a

special place in the history of the Kazakh press.

In general, the importance of the Kazakh press was defined by A. Baitursynov, M. Dulatov, S. Seifullin, M. Aueyev, Sh. Tokzhigitov, M. Turganbayev, Zh. Aimauytov and other Kazakh intellectuals in periodicals. And at that time, A. Baitursynov said "A newspaper is the eyes, ears and tongue of the nation. The people need the eyes, the ears, the tongue, and it means the people need the newspaper as well. The newspaper speaks for the people, complains, defends their interests, resists the cry" (Kazakh, 1998). It shows that the newspaper attaches great importance to its place in society.

Today, the role of the press has grown even more. It is known that the workload of the press is not measured by its number, but by its activities based on national interests. In this regard, the First President Nursultan Nazarbayev praised the role of the press in our society: "Due to the current socio-economic situation, the nature and desires of the reader, the press now has an educational, cognitive, Kazakhstan patriotism. Because we are building a new state. Therefore, in such a crisis, the press must ensure that the political thought that promotes a unifying society is at the forefront. Therefore, I do not understand how to conduct your own policy and explain the essence of the reform, without relying on the cognitive, thoughtful press as a force for the formation of the state" (Meeting with, 1994).

Author has combined the views and opinions of such prominent figures as A. Baitursynov, A. Bokeikhanov, M. Dulatov, M. Turganbayev, who defined the importance of the Kazakh press on modern historical concepts. The study of periodicals in Kazakhstan was guided by the scientific findings and conclusions of such scientists as B. Kenzhebayev, H. Bekhozhin, T. Kozhakeev, U. Subkhanberdina, K. Atabaev, K. Allabergenov. All the research has done based on the scientific works of historians, such as K. Nurpeisov, M. Kozybayev, M. Koigeldiev, T. Omarbekov and others were involved in the disclosure of the public activities of the newspapers that were the Bolshevik press. The research works of S. Tabarikuly, A. Espenbetov, R. Moldasheva, S. Smagulova, V. Kashlyak, D. Makhat, who considered the history of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" and its place in the socio-cultural life of Kazakhstan in the context of today's requirements were widely used by the author.

The work provides new insights into the history of the newspaper:

Implementation of the disclosure of the preconditions for the emergence and formation of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili";

The publication of the Soviet-era publication increased the socio-political consciousness of the population and their active participation in Soviet events;

Mastering the ability to classify the structure, size, circulation, names, features and characteristics of the headlines of the newspaper;

Cultural and educational activities of the organizers and correspondents of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" among the masses, the formation of an analysis of the views and conclusions of the nation's intellectuals in this area;

Mastering the data-based analysis of the activities of national intellectuals such as M. Turganbayev, M. Auezov, Sh. Tokzhigitov, Zh. Aimaurov, S. Dunentaev in the publication and formation of its work;

Formation of the ability to analyze socio-political and socio-economic issues on the pages of the publication;

To analyze and determine on the basis of printed materials the impact of the newspaper on the education and involvement of Kazakh youth and women in the work of society at that time.

This work is based on the history of the formation and edition of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", published in Semipalatinsk between the years of 1919-1928, which also were considered the structure of the newspaper, archival data on the newspaper's publishers, organizers and authors, original materials of the newspaper, significant scientific works and scientific articles. This textbook, which tells the story of the publication of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", is valuable in that it includes scientific articles published in the pages of the edition. The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" and the issues of development of the Kazakh society, the rise of socio-political issues in the newspaper, the socio-economic situation in Kazakhstan, the cultural development of Kazakhstan are analyzed in detail in the newspaper. This work is intended for readers who want to get acquainted with the history of the Kazakh press.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The beginning of the XX century is a period full of historical events. The news of the victory of the revolutionary forces led by Lenin in Petrograd in October of 1917, the overthrow of the Provisional Government and the transfer of state power to the Soviets shook not only the whole of Russia, but the whole world. This event coincided with the establishment and strengthening of Soviet power in the central and distant regions of Russia. In many

places it was carried out without bloodshed under the influence of the central districts.

The call for national equality and liberation was banned with the coming to power of the Soviet government, which began with the political changes in the Russian Empire as a result of the Russian revolutions of 1905-1907 years and after the February Revolution of 1917, the national consciousness was forbidden, and the doctrine of democracy and equality ceased to exist for a long time. One of the first activities of the Soviet government in Kazakhstan was the propagation of communist doctrine. Particular attention was paid to the press in this capacity. For this purpose, the Soviet authorities suspended the work of Kazakh-language newspapers such as "Kazakh", "Saryarka", "Abai", "Alash", "Zhas Azamat", "Birlik Tuy", concluding that they were nationalist, authoritative and as Alashorda's notions.

The Soviet authorities ordered the closure of newspapers and magazines published in the national language and the transfer of all printing equipment to the Military Revolutionary Committee for the Management of the Kazakh Territory (KROMA). Now the local press had to carry out propaganda and organizational work for the Soviet government to send workers to the struggle.

For this purpose, the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" is published in Semipalatinsk as a body of the provincial revolutionary committee (Bekkhoshin, 1964). There is a lot of information about the publication of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili". Archival data show that the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was published on the 4th of December, 1919 (KRPM). T. Kozhekeyev writes about the first Soviet edition published in Semipalatinsk: "On the 1st of December, 1919, the workers and garrison troops led by the Bolsheviks defeated the White Guards and handed over power to the Military Revolutionary Committee".

With the cleansing of the city from the Kolchak gangs, namely, on the 4th of December was published the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", a body of the Semipalatinsk Provincial Committee and the Regional Committee (Kozhakeev, 1991). Muksyn Kordabayev, a publisher who participated in the publication of the first issue, wrote in his article "How we published the first issue": "Thus, the Soviet power was re-established in Semipalatinsk on the 1st December, 1919. Semipalatinsk printing houses were taken over by the state and it was decided to publish a Soviet Kazakh newspaper in the province. The newspaper was named "Qazaq Tili" (Kordabaev, 1969), in the next memoir, "This is

how the first issue came out" it is known that "until November of 1919, the newspaper "Saryarka" was published in Semipalatinsk under the influence of Alashorda. On the 1st December of that year, the city fell to the Reds and Soviet power was restored. Thus, along with other small enterprises, the printing house was taken over by the state, and a decision was made to publish a Bolshevik-oriented Kazakh newspaper in the province called "Qazaq Tili" (Kordabaev).

After the establishment of Soviet power in Semipalatinsk, the printing house "Zhardem" was also taken over by the Semipalatinsk Provincial Revolutionary Committee. The first issues of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" were published by "Zhardem" publishing house. The main organizers of the publishing house "Zhardem" ("Alashorda") were Sadyk Nigmatullin, Sultan Nigmatullin, Akhmetzhan Nigmatullin (Kazbalinov, 2003). After the February Revolution of 1917, the "Zhardem" printing house was purchased by the Semipalatinsk regional Kazakh committee from the fraternal Tatar merchants Nigmattulin family. This lithographic printing house was brought from Tomsk in 1910 (Sydykov, 2010). The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was later published by the Semipalatinsk regional publishing house.

3. METHODOLOGY

Regarding the history of the newspaper's publication, Kaiken Shamkin wrote in an article "Holding hands with journalists": "In 1917-1919 years, there were four small printing houses in Semipalatinsk. One of them was in the house next to the house of culture of the company "Bolshevichka", next to the shop of the bakery. This is the printing house of the famous Semipalatinsk monopolist Pleshcheev. The second was in the house where today's regional military commissariat is located. The third is a printing house of a rich man named Pechenkin in a house on the present-day Mukhtar Auezov Street. The fourth is the above-mentioned Kazakh publishing house "Yardam". At the end of February of 1922, all of the above printing houses were merged and relocated to the present-day Baurzhan Momysuly Street, 16" (Shamkin, 1964).

From December 1919 to 1922 the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was published by the printing house "Alashorda" ("Zhardem") in Semipalatinsk (Alash), and from the end of February 1922 to the 17th of March, 1928 the Semipalatinsk regional printing house was published by the present joint-stock company "Semey Polygraphy".

There is a lot of information about the number of times the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was published. One of them states that the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was first published once a week, and later three times (Kozhakeev, 1991). According to the archives of Semipalatinsk, the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was published twice a week (East Kazakhstan). In the first years of its existence, the volume of the newspaper was two pages (The Kazakh language, 1921), later four pages (The Kazakh language, 1923), in subsequent years it was six and eight pages (The Kazakh language, 1925).

The situation with the publication of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" can be seen in the article "More than the five thousand" published in the issue dated on the 13th of November, 1923. The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was published at a time when the Kazakh allies (communists) could not be formed. At that time, there were almost no people among the population who knew about the road design and construction of the Soviet government. It is said "The Kazakh language took a risk and served the Kazakh workers in such a turbulent time" (Bekkhochin, 1981).

From this we can see that after the establishment of the Soviet government, the Kazakh intellectuals, which had gathered around the newspaper, continued to publish in Semipalatinsk as a successor, despite the closure of the national publications founded by Alash figures.

As for the cover of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", in the middle of the first page there was "Kyrgyz Gazeti", at the bottom of which was the title of the publication and "Kyrgyz Sozi" in Russian. The word "Qazaq Tili" was written in Arabic on the right forehead of this page.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This seemed to be an internal protest against the mistaken name of yesterday's the Russians "Kyrgyz". The title of the edition "Qazaq Tili" is very important. Why the newspaper was called "Qazaq Tili": "The newspaper is the first tool to understand what the people need, grievances or shortcomings in order to be popular, whether it is convenient for the people, or uncomfortable, what is happening in other countries. Everyone uses this tool to their advantage. Not only one person writes in the newspaper, but many people from different places write useful and big problems of life for the people. Therefore, reading, listening to the newspaper, writing words, bring innumerable benefits to the people... In short, the newspaper has become a tool for the poor and workers.

Hardworking youth! Do not use your own tools, wake up, not the time for sleeping" (October revolution, 1921), these statements can be seen from the comments of the edition on behalf of the publishers.

Historian Musatay Akynzhanov in his memoir "Semey morning" - "Qazaq Tili" which was the first Soviet Kazakh press, he said: "On the night of the establishment of Soviet power in Semipalatinsk, Muksyn unpacked the newspaper "Saryarka", which had been collected on the other side of the Irtysh, and which had been came by boat that night, M. Auezov, M. Turganbayev and others suggested renaming the newspaper to "Qazaq Tili" (Akynzhanov M). This shows the continuity between the newspapers "Saryarka" and "Qazaq Tili". Muksyn Kordabayev was one of the young people who published the newspaper "Saryarka" and typed the first issues of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", Mukhtar Auezov was a prominent author of the newspaper "Saryarka" and editor of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili". This step of our honorable persons shows the publication of the first national publication in Soviet Kazakhstan "Qazaq Tili", which followed in the footsteps of the Kazakh-language newspaper "Saryarka" in Semipalatinsk.

A comparative perspective shows that "Qazaq Tili" developed both in continuity with and in distinction from other contemporary Kazakh-language publications, particularly "Saryarka" and "Abai". While "Saryarka" was more closely associated with the Alash-centered national political agenda and "Abai" had a stronger literary and intellectual orientation, "Qazaq Tili" combined political reporting with practical materials on public education, women's issues, local administration, and rural life. This made its structure more functionally diverse and better adapted to the emerging Soviet public sphere. At the same time, the newspaper preserved important features of national public communication, which allowed it to serve as a transitional platform between the earlier national press tradition and the new Soviet media order.

The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was born to convey the needs and aspirations of the general public. Thus, the title and content of the publication were intertwined. The article "Five wishes for five years" which had dedicated to the anniversary of the "Qazaq Tili" were written: "And here it is, on the 4th of December the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" will be five years old. There is no bigger Kazakh newspaper than the "Qazaq Tili". The Board is preparing to celebrate a five-year anniversary. We intend to start

the day with good wishes and slogans. The great task of the five-year anniversary is to increase the importance of the newspaper, to bring it closer to the local people and to bring it to the level of real armaments for the benefit of the country".

"...The current motto of the five-year anniversary clock, which were already ticking to a six-year anniversary clock was "The desire to increase the number of the "Qazaq Tili" newspaper to five thousand in order to be in line with the times and the epoch. This is our third task.

...Trying to fulfill the tasks of the party, the social duty, the work of the state is a major task of all party members for the citizens of the state, social business. It is a common duty to try to fulfill it, and it is hoped that it will help many people" (Five wishes, 1924), and this clearly shows that the main goal is to meet the needs and aspirations of the people.

The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" published materials on socio-political, socio-economic, and cultural issues in a clearly organized internal structure. The thematic range of the publication was distributed across several recurring columns, where the leading space was devoted to socio-political discussion, while the subsequent sections focused on socio-economic conditions, cultural life, and public announcements. This arrangement indicates that the newspaper followed a stable editorial logic and sought to balance ideological, informational, and educational functions.

The document from the archives contains various additions to expand the content and importance of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", such as the development of resolutions of the Congress of the Communist Party of Russia (Bolsheviks), the unified farming tax, strengthening the press, methods of farming development, land issues, cooperation, and the fight against old customs, public education, health and cleanliness were in the forefront matter. The intellectuals of the nation, such as Sh. Tokzhigitov, M. Turganbayev, A. Dossov, G. Ismagulov, A. Elshibekov were responsible for overseeing the publication of materials on these topics in the newspaper (EKR).

The following information is given about the headings, distribution, responsible publishers of materials published in the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" during the first eight years of the twentieth century. In 1919, the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was the press organ of the Semipalatinsk Revolutionary Committee in Semipalatinsk (Bekkhochin, 1964).

In 1920, the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", published as a body of the Semipalatinsk Provincial Executive

Committee, published articles on life abroad, Soviet Russia, Kazakhstan, party life, working life, peasant life, local life, women's equality. That year it was published under the editorship of M. Turganbayev, Zh. Aimaityov, M. Auezov and on behalf of the editorial board (The Kazakh).

In the first years the circulation of the newspaper was 2500 copies (Kozhakeev, 1991). Then in 1921 the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was published on behalf of the Semipalatinsk Provincial Executive Committee and the Provincial Committee. The editorial board of the newspaper, which was published under the headings of national news, domestic news, foreign news, Soviet Russia, Kazakhstan, the official section, advertising, women's equality, Kazakh workers, had a circulation of 4000, 6000, 3000 copies (The Kazakh, 1920). Shaimardan Tokzhigitov was the editor of the newspaper in 1922, which published articles on foreign news, internal news, the official section, local news, women's equality, national news, party life, the response from the administration, the life of workers. The level of circulation of the newspaper varies, showing 700, 600, 500, 1000, 2000, 3000 copies (The Kazakh, 1921).

In general, due to the merger of all private printing houses in Semipalatinsk with the regional printing house, the circulation of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" decreased to 600 copies (Kashlyak, 2008).

Then, in 1923, the newspaper covered foreign affairs, internal affairs, national affairs, party life, the official section, the life of workers, women's equality. That year Sh. Tokzhigitov will be the editor of the newspaper with a circulation of 700, 1000, 2450, 2300, 3200, 2700 copies. In addition, the temporary publishers of the newspaper were Zh. Tattibayev, A. Dossov, Zh. Naimangozhin (The Kazakh, 1923).

In 1924, Sh. Tokzhigitov was the editor-in-chief of the newspaper, which published various articles on national affairs, party life, official affairs, workers' life, foreign affairs, internal affairs, women's equality, and youth life and a temporary issuer was Zh. Naimangozhin. Also, the publication of the Communist Party of Russia (Bolsheviks) as a body of the Semipalatinsk Provincial Executive Council and the Provincial Committee and the Provincial Trade Union Council was distributed in 1400, 1150, 1000, 950, 700, 2100 copies (The Kazakh, 1924)

The scope of newspaper headlines expanded and the topics changed from 1925 to 1928 years. For example, in 1925 the newspaper was published under the following headings. In particular, in the

villages, abroad, in the Soviet Union, in the peasantry, in party life, in cooperation, in the Soviet election campaign, in the educational field, in litigation, among women, youth life, the tax season, and more.

Shaimardan Tokzhigitov and Uali Zabiroy worked as editors of the "Qazaq Tili" newspaper, while Karim Toktabayevich and Zhumazhan Tattibayev worked as temporary editors in 1925 (The Kazakh, 1925).

Issues of 1926 were published under the headings, such as in our province, news of Chinese events, know the laborer, know the cattle breeding, health, wealth, court cases, foreign news, in the villages, abroad, in the Soviet Union, about the peasantry, party life, cooperation, the Soviet election campaign, in the field of education, litigation, among women, youth, and more, the tax season. The editor-in-chief of the newspaper was U. Zabiroy in 1926, and the temporary publishers were S. Arykov and A. Saidalin. It is also published on behalf of the editorial board (The Kazakh, 1926).

In 1927, the responsible publishers of the publication were such national intellectuals as D. Sharapiev, I. Toktybayev, B. Aibasov, M. Beissenov, A. Ismailov. The newspaper was written about the Soviet election campaign, the Soviet election campaign, the country's economy, educational work in the country, married life, answers to questions, answers from the administration, one by one, in the center of Kazakhstan, about poverty, abroad, about cooperation, women, districts, and materials with headings as the tax season were also published (The Kazakh, 1927).

In 1928 on the pages of the publication were various small messages, Moscow messages, the need to strengthen the economy, party life, in the provinces of Kazakhstan, Soviet construction, primary wealth, health, various letters from within the country, answers to questions, answers from the administration, advertising, country, also there were articles on mutual taxation, socio-political, socio-economic and cultural issues among Kazakh women, also educational work in the country, cooperatives of the country. That year the editors of the newspaper were A. Ismailov, A. Nagymzhan, G. Iskakov (The Kazakh, 1928).

Structurally, the newspaper demonstrated a gradual institutionalization of editorial practice. Its development can be traced through changes in publication frequency, page volume, circulation, editorial responsibility, and the expansion of headings across different years. These changes show that "Qazaq Tili" functioned not only as a source of

information, but also as an organized communication platform reflecting political priorities, educational tasks, and socio-cultural transformation in Semipalatinsk and the broader Kazakh region. The diversification of sections and the increasing thematic range indicate the newspaper's transition from a narrowly political publication into a multi-functional public medium.

The directions and topics of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" can be clearly seen in the articles published in it. Materials of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" can be grouped and divided in terms of content as follows. There were socio-political, socio-economic articles, literary works, educational work among the Kazakhs, the main place of the mother tongue, language issues, the status of Kazakh women, freedom, equality, medical, agro-technical advice, scientific achievements, internal and external news, correspondent letters, reply letters.

However, analyzing the newspaper materials, it should be noted that the publication focused on the strengthening of the Soviet government, party policy, and campaign activities. Therefore, every issue of the Soviet-era newspaper must be sent to the regional party committee, the republic, the propaganda department of the Central Committee, to the archives, to large libraries. Each issue of the publication was read, analyzed, and reviewed. There were also reasons why the Soviet government paid close attention to this publication and kept it under strict control. After all, the publishers of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" were M. Turganbayev, Sh. Tokzhigitov, M. Auezov, Zh. Aimauytov, S. Saduakasov, N. Nurmakov and other Kazakh intellectuals. Their opinions and conclusions and valuable articles were published in the newspaper.

The press department of the Central Committee received a monthly report on the publication, filled out a questionnaire containing all the information about the newspaper and provided various information.

One of them states that the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was regularly sent to the press department of the Central Committee. For example, if 25 copies of the newspaper had sent in 1922, in that same year from the 1st of November 8 copies would be sent (EKR).

The document signed by Comrade I. Stalin, the Secretary of the Central Committee, states that five copies of books and periodicals published in Semipalatinsk since the 12th of December, 1922 should be sent to the Semipalatinsk Provincial Executive Committee (EKR). Each issue of the newspaper, published in the Soviet era, must be sent

to the regional party committee, the republic, the propaganda department of the Central Committee, to the archives, to the large libraries. There were read the contents of periodicals and analyzed the materials. At times, they even commented on the publication. For example, the press service of the Kyrgyz (Kazakh) regional committee also commented on the newspaper as in the following: "In the press department of the Kyrgyz Regional Committee of the Russian Communist Party (Bolsheviks), according to your proposal, I have viewed 19 copies of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", the organ of the Semipalatinsk Provincial Executive Committee and the Provincial Committee of the Russian Communist Party (Bolsheviks) from the 12th of April to the 22th of June, inclusive, and I give the following review: Paper, print, type, spelling, distribution of materials, in general, the entire technical side of the newspaper was delivered satisfactorily. Questions about the units, agricultural tax, about the state fear, about the people's court, etc. were raised on the newspaper.

But these coverage is often only informational in nature without detailed specification. Most of the articles are written extensively and at full length. The syllable of the newspaper is heavy, bookish, so reading it seems very boring to me.

Almost nothing is written in the newspaper about the organizations of women, about the organizations of youth, about factory apprenticeships (there are workers' districts in Semipalatinsk Gubernia), nothing is written about the improvement and condition of agriculture, nothing has been written about cooperation and the state of the harvest, whereas the question of the copied working population is a question of why it would be necessary to popularize this question and make the working reader public.

The political line of the newspaper is generally correct, but it is necessary to simplify the form of presentation, coverage and specific guidance for organizing youth, copying from the local population and attracting ordinary employees from the field. In addition, the newspaper must vigilantly follow and publish with clarifications those originating from the Center of the KSSR. Party, professional and Soviet actions and dispossession, and not limited to the publication of such bodies and the Center of the Federation" (KRPM). From this comment can be seen that the newspaper criticized the lack of coverage of party life. All of this suggests that the post-Soviet press was tough.

The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" is distributed in Semipalatinsk, Pavlodar, Ust-Kamenogorsk, Zaisan

and Karkaralinsk districts. In addition to these regions of Kazakhstan, it is also widespread in Mongolia. According to a document from the archives, Mongolia has been borrowing the "Qazaq Tili" newspaper since 1920. Later, when the name of the publication was changed, five copies of the newspaper were sent to the appropriate place (EKR).

In 1920-1925 years, there were about 15 newspapers and magazines in Soviet Kazakhstan, one of which was the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", published in Semipalatinsk from the 4th of December, 1919 to March 1928 (Kenzhebeyev, Kozhakeev, 1962).

There is a lot of information about the circulation of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili". In the first years, the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" reached 600-700 copies, and later - up to 6000 copies. Of course, the newspaper has not always remained the same and has not grown. The "Qazaq Tili" has experienced periods of growth and decline, which is typical for all publications.

First of all, based on the original newspaper, it can be provided the following information. For example, 4000, 6000, 3000, 700 copies in 1921; 700, 600, 500, 1000, 3000 copies in 1922; 700, 1000, 2450, 2700 copies in 1923; 1450, 1600, 500, 600, 1000, 2000 copies in 1924; 1000, 1200 copies in 1925; 550-1100 copies in 1926; 1350-4200 copies in 1927 and 1600-2700 copies in 1928 (see Appendix) (The Kazakh, 1921). According to archival data, the circulation of the newspaper increased to 700 copies in the first year, then in 1922-1923 years it was raised to 1000 copies in January, 1000 copies in February, 1600 copies in March, 2300 copies in April, 2700 copies in May, 2250 copies in June, 2300 copies in July, 2250 copies in August, 2000 copies in September, and it indicates a deceleration rate (KRPM). Documents from the archives also confirm that the newspaper was published in 2000-2500 copies (KRPM). It should be noted that the newspaper's circulation was sharply reduced.

Ilyas Moldazhanov, a well-known author of the publication, who paid special attention to the growth of the newspaper's circulation, wrote in his article "Press work": "The newspaper is my eyes, my ears, my knees and my guide". And communicate as much as possible and distribute to the country: it is the duty of the workers, the poor in the steppes and the general population to not only give free money and receive newspapers, but also to write, to be a representative, and to put their opinions on the front line. It is our human duty to fulfill these tasks, and we must work together and

bear fruit, not forgetting the task. To increase the number and importance of the newspaper, to be a wise man, a leader, a mirror to see, to correct, to be the first weapon in the narrow struggle, both on the ridge and in the city, among the workers. Only then will the goal be achieved" (Moldazhanov, 1924). At that time, there were local correspondents of the "Qazaq Tili" newspaper.

In an open letter to journalists of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili": "Given the importance of the press in general, and its wide access to the Kazakh press in particular, and the fact that the newspaper often fails to meet the needs of large numbers of workers, the Semipalatinsk Regional Executive Committee, the Provincial Committee of the Commonwealth and the "Qazaq Tili" newspaper invites you to write a word. To do this, it is necessary to constantly send information about the lives of those workers, about the work of various courts, and about the issues that determine the structure of our peasantry. It is important to remember that the newspaper is not only a wise man who preach, but also a letter writer in the process of developing the peasantry and raising the cultural level of the people. We need the newspaper to be a mentor and teacher of the Kazakh people in the right sense. We hope that you will support our appeal" said the journalist's comrades... We are confident that these comrades will not hesitate to respond to our call, and will consider this task as their duty (Tokzhigitov, 1923), so it emphasizes the role of the newspaper in society and helps to make the content of the publication.

Numerous correspondence was published in special issues of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili". Their content is also diverse: full of ideas, suggestions, everyday life. There are also issues that need to be considered. All this has been studied, checked and published. It is a well-established tradition to pay attention to the publication of letters from readers of the newspaper. This tradition was formed and spread in the "Qazaq Tili". Let's prove it. 87 people wrote letters to the "Qazaq Tili" in 1925; in 1927 - 135, and in 1928 - 167 people wrote letters (Semipalatinsk morning, 1969). If we look, we can consider that the number of journalists is growing every year.

The "Qazaq Tili" newspaper, one of the Soviet Kazakh periodicals, was published from the 4th of December, 1919 to March 1928. Publishers, author-correspondents of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" were such Alash figures as M. Turganbayev, M. Auezov, Zh. Aimauytov, Sh. Tokzhigitov, S. Donentaev, S. Toraigyrov, Sh. Kudaiberdiev, M. Dulatov, Sh. Musataiuly, Sh. Kereibayev, I. Alimbekov. These

citizens and their trusted companions introduced the "Qazaq Tili" as a follower of the "Kazakh" and "Saryarka" newspapers, which rose to the status of a national publication.

There were difficulties during the publication of the newspaper. They were, first of all, a financial issue, and then the "vigilant source" of the Soviet government. At the time of publication of the first issues of the newspaper, the capacity of the printing house was limited. The shortage of professionals and printing equipment caused a number of difficulties during the publication.

The main difficulties were as follows: "How difficult it is to publish a newspaper in the conditions of printing, which is scarce and worn out. Working with Arabic letters, many of which are full of dots, seems to have doubled that difficulty. After the first two pages of the newspaper were printed and left the machine, the missing letters had to be pulled out and typed into the last two pages. On the one hand, this was a hindrance, and on the other hand, the name of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", which makes the press unsteady, was not capitalized in Arabic, so we used to carve a wooden shoe for a skilled shoemaker" (Kordabaev). Despite the unfavorable conditions, the publishers regularly published the newspaper.

At the same time, Kazakh intellectuals such as Akhmetzhan Kozbagaruly, Abulhair Dossov, Shynzhy Kereibaiuly, Abzal Zhiengaliyev, Zhumat Shanin provided financial support to the publication. They intensified the printing business and contributed to the growth of newspaper circulation. The newspaper expressed its gratitude for the financial assistance provided to the publishing house "Qazaq Tili". In one of them: the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" received more letters from October and strengthened its printing house. It was financially secure. We are grateful to the chairman of the Semipalatinsk regional committee Dosuly, the commissioner of food of Kazakhstan Samatuly, the chairman of the Semipalatinsk regional union Ivanov, and the member of the board Alikhanovuly. They were the board of writers of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" (Thanks, 1924). Insufficient funding for the newspaper can also be seen in the articles published in the newspaper.

Mannan Turganbayev wrote in the article "Assistance to the newspaper" published in the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" on the 20th of November, 1923 on the issue of finances: "With the advent of paid advertising, both in the past and in the present, the newspaper's funds are often collected from advertisements and expressions. A newspaper that

can't get help from advertisements and expressions can't stand on its own two feet. The national equation is only through science and culture. A country without science and culture cannot have this right. The Kazakh poor people were given the right.

The government of Kazakhstan was formed. However, there are many shortcomings among the poor Kazakhs. With this in mind, Kazakh citizens should not only be proud of their rights, but also pay more attention to the dissemination of science and culture among the people.

From the very beginning, the management of the "Qazaq Tili" was determined to carry out its duties. The statement sent in Russian, the advertisements are immediately translated into Kazakh and published without delay. The "Qazaq Tili" newspaper department invites intelligent Kazakh citizens to help. There is a lot of work to be done" (Qazaq Tili, 1923). Emphasizing the importance of the press, the author invites Kazakh readers to work together for the prosperity of the newspaper, despite the fact that it receives money from advertising.

We call the "Qazaq Tili" - the Kazakh Soviet press. After all, this newspaper was the first to introduce the Soviet government to the Kazakh village, to spread the party's policy, the idea of Leninism to the Kazakh people. This was the direction of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili". The "Qazaq Tili" newspaper could be step by step with the modern edition, as it explains this step as follows: "On the 4th of December marks the 5th anniversary of the publication of "Qazaq Tili". In terms of age, the "Qazaq Tili" is the brother of Kazakh newspapers published during the Soviet era...

Many citizens of Kazakhstan know what hardships the "Qazaq Tili" has gone through in the last five years. Of course, there are a lot of difficulties. Even with these 5th anniversary to the 6th, we can't say that all the obstacles and difficulties in the way of the "Qazaq Tili" have disappeared. Even at this age, the number of issues of the "Qazaq Tili" is still around. This illustration shows some of the challenges we face. We do not hide the fact that these shortcomings will continue. We are confident that with the help of many people we will be able to get rid of the burden quickly.

The Kazakh workers, who were oppressed, kicked and left in the dark, with the intention to cut the roots of the old life and start a new life, were brought to light. The "Qazaq Tili" newspaper, which has taken on the task together with the

Communist Party, says that it will be able to justify its position on the occasion of its 5th anniversary with the help of all its supporters (Dear friend, 1924).

From the very beginning, the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was able to unite the Kazakh youth in the city and the countryside in its propaganda and organizational work. This is evidenced by the opening of a special youth page "Enbekshil Zhas" in the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" on the 22 th of January, 1923 (Hardworking young people, 1923).

"Enbekshil Zhas" was published as a page on the 22 th of January, 1923, and on the 7th of January, 1925, as a supplement to the "Qazaq Tili", it was published once every seven days as a special four-page youth newspaper (Hardworking young man, 1925). It can find in the archives about a release of "Enbekshil Zhas". In the content of the document, the agenda of the meeting of the Secretariat of the Russian Communist Party (Bolsheviks) of the Provincial Committee considers the issue of the opening of the "Enbekshil Zhas" and approves the resolution (KRPM).

Shaimardan Tokzhigitov was the main organizer of the youth page "Enbekshil Zhas" in the newspaper "Qazaq Tili". On the first page of "Enbekshil Zhas" was published an article "This is the goal" by Sh. Tokzhigitov. Also he said: "The purpose of this newspaper is stated above. Thinking about the disadvantages of the Kazakh working youth, I would like to introduce as much as possible the common way of working youth and hard-working Kazakh youth. We introduce hard-working Kazakh youth, showing the direction of youth, the state of youth flow, and the main goal is to include Kazakh youth to the society" (Tokzhigitov, 1924).

The youth page "Enbekshil Zhas" attracted young people from the then Komsomol organizations, students of pedagogical colleges in Semipalatinsk, distant villages and Bolsheviks.

Historian Musatai Akynzhanov and well-known author Saki Beisebayev were the publishers of the "Enbekshil Zhas" page. Musatai Akynzhanov told about the publication of "Enbekshil Zhas": "Although I did not work in the newspaper at that time, I was considered a key employee of the newspaper, and the newspaper trusted me and I headed the Komsomol youth department. Through that section, we inherited from the 4th page of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" and organized our own page "Enbekshil Zhas". I was with its editor Saki Beisebayev. We have published 7-8 pages of "Enbekshil Zhas". On behalf of the provincial youth organization, the publishers visited the villages and

organized material for the newspaper" (Akynzhanov).

The biography of Saki Beisebayev, the head of the youth page, was found in the archives of Semey. The document contains information that S. Beisebayev was the editor of the "Enbekshil Zhas" page on the 1st of October, 1923 (EKR).

Many letters of support and congratulations were received in support of the opening of the "Enbekshil Zhas" youth page. And in one of them: "Our Kazakh youth also began to publish their own newspaper - "Enbekshil Zhas". The main purpose of the newspaper "Enbekshil Zhas" gives the Kazakh people a sense of the rightness of the work they started, albeit difficult, and the inexhaustible energy of the working Kazakh youth, the confidence that the work will be completed" [56]. And the other: "Our Kazakh youth began to publish their own newspaper. Its name is "Enbekshil Zhas". The main goal of the newspaper "Enbekshil Zhas" is to educate citizens who fight for socialism and build a future socialist society (Tokzhigitov, 1924).

Saki Beisebayev's poem "Congratulations" dedicated to the "Enbekshil Zhas" is still out of the spotlight. In the author's poem:

Let's burn! Let's burn! Don't turn "yourself" off!
Come up the youth! Come up! Come up!
Congratulations to "Enbekshil Zhas"!
The common ground is the same way.

Precious to young people,
Respect for young people,

Let the "Enbekshil Zhas" do it! (Stepnaya Pravda, 1925) - he once again showed that young people are the continuator of all hopes and good deeds.

The board of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" in its message to readers: "The newspaper "Enbekshil Zhas" was delayed for various reasons. We apologize to our students. From now on, "Enbekshil Zhas" will not be a page, but will be published as a newspaper in addition to "Qazaq Tili" (Beisebaev, 1923), which deepens the purpose and content of the publication".

S. Arykov worked as an editor of the special youth page "Enbekshil Zhas" from the 10th of October, 1924 (To our students, 1925).

The youth edition "Enbekshil Zhas" raised the issues of education of Kazakh women and girls, the life of young people in the city and the countryside, the elimination of illiteracy among young people. Special mention should be made of the article "Labor laws must be enforced" published in the 7th of January, 1925 issue of the "Enbekshil Zhas". The author writes that the implementation of labor laws

is a guarantee of protection of the rights of young people, for which the provincial, district youth committees, trade unions must work together as one: "In general, it is a question of the priority of the comrade appointed for office work among young people: first of all, exactly to whom will serve the farmhand children in the designated area. If there is no committee of tenants between the rich and the hired, then at any age they sign contracts through the organization of foresters, express their rights to them, provide them with political education, and invite them to a common youth organization should be introduced. Only then will we be able to fulfill our mission by increasing the number of like-minded young members of our organization, and on the other hand, by bringing to light the young people who are crushed in the dark, working day and night and earning a living wage" (KRPM).

The content of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" has expanded and the range of topics has expanded. The newspaper was faced with such difficult tasks as improving the quality of the publication, increasing its circulation, increasing the number of journalists. The celebration of the fifth anniversary of the publication of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was started in 1924. The main organizers of the newspaper were Sh. Tokzhigitov, Sh. Zhantileuov, Zh. Shanin, M. Auezov, G. Ismagulov. During the celebration of the fifth anniversary of the publication, special attention was paid to improving the quality and expanding the circulation of the newspaper and the selection of journalists (Taukekanuly, 1925).

The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was able to contribute to the formation of public opinion and mobilize the masses. On the pages of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" raised topical issues such as health, language, education, women's issues were the articles by M. Turganbayev, M. Auezov, Zh. Aimauytov, Sh. Tokzhigitov, S. Dunentaev, I. Moldazhanov, Zh. Tattibayev and other intellectuals of the nation, which were often published. The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" played a special role in awakening and giving impetus to the consciousness of our people, frozen by the colonial policy of the Russian Empire.

In the history of the Kazakh press there are many publications published by individuals, including M. Turganbayev, M. Auezov, Zh. Aimauytov, S. Saduakasov, Sh. Tokzhigitov, N. Nurmakov, A. Dossov, I. Toktybayev, M. Dulatov and others. The "Qazaq Tili" newspaper is one of the most active in the nation's intellectuals.

The "Qazaq Tili" newspaper was angered by

Stalin, who ruled the Soviet Union on his own. In order to set up a newspaper that Stalin considered to be nationalist, he gave the following clear instructions to the party leadership: "I am against the involvement of non-party intellectuals in the political and ideological education of Kyrgyz youth. We did not take power to hand over the education of young people to bourgeois intellectuals who are not in the party. This whole battle must be left to the Communists" (EKR). Following the instructions, the party leadership began to establish strict control over the media in the country.

Kazakh-language periodicals published in Kazakhstan fill out questionnaires on a monthly basis. Their content was also carefully checked. This is stated in a document from the archives: "The "Qazaq Tili" is almost not interested in party life in the localities and in the Center, not a single word is mentioned during 3 months about the party conferences of its provinces, not to mention others" (The truth, 1993). This indicates that party control of periodicals was tight.

5. CONCLUSION

The name of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", published in Semipalatinsk on the 4th of December, 1919, it was going to be changed in 1928. In this regard, a document from the archives at the meeting of the propaganda department of the Semipalatinsk Provincial Executive Committee on the 8th of March, 1928 adopted a resolution to change the name of the newspaper. Based on this decree, in March 1928, the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was renamed "Zhana Auy" (KRPM).

Continuing the tradition of the Kazakh newspaper, it was Alibi Zhangeldin who denounced the nationalist orientation of the "Ak Zhol" newspaper and used it as evidence in his political struggle with the Alash Orda. Regarding this issue, D. Amanzholova said: "For the same loyal Leninists-Stalinists and longtime enemies of Alash, like A. Zhangeldin, the very fact of participation in the democratic national press of a non-Bolnevist trend served as a true proof of counter-revolutionary, which he reported to V.I. Lenin in April 1921, referring to the biography of N. Torekulov and S. Khodzhanov - the leaders of Soviet Turkestan" (KRPM). Although this argument seems to be devoted to the political events in the Turkestan region, its coldness was directly related to the "Qazaq Tili" newspaper, which was published in Semipalatinsk in 1919-1928 years.

The renaming of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" coincides with the fact that in 1928 the first group of

Alash activists became "enemies of the people". At the same time, the "Qazaq Tili" newspaper was renamed "Zhana Auyl".

Thus, the newspaper "Qazaq Tili", published in Semipalatinsk from the 4th of December, 1919 to March 1928 by Akhmet Baitursynov in Arabic, was now published in Latin under the name "Zhana Auyl". For instance, Muksyn Kordabayev said: "In one of the bureaus of the district committee, the secretary of the regional party committee Goloshchekin took part and decided that "only Russian language newspapers should be left in the city, and Kazakh newspapers should be given to the district". According to that decision, the "Zhana Auyl" was transferred to Ayakoz, and I was appointed as an editor" (Amanzholova, 2009). In 1928 M. Turganbayev, M. Auezov, Zh. Aimauytov, Sh. Tokzhigitov, S. Dumentaev and others national intellectuals, who published the first national newspaper in Soviet Kazakhstan, the "Qazaq Tili", were also politically accused and subjected to Stalinist repression.

The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" provided a wealth of information as a source for understanding the development trends of Kazakh society. Recognition

of the history of the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" allows future generations to get acquainted with the socio-political, socio-economic and literary-cultural life of our people at that time.

The "Qazaq Tili" newspaper is a publication that mourns the needs of the people and unites Kazakh citizens in this way. It is known that the activity of the press in general is measured by its activity based on the national interest. If we look at the history of the publication, which today is a propagandist of popular issues and an organizer of the masses, it appeared and continued its work during the turbulent period in the Irtysh region after the October Revolution. After the establishment of the Soviet government, newspapers were established in the region to set and propagate their policies. Although the newspaper "Qazaq Tili" was the first bulletin of the Soviet Kazakh press, it mainly acted as a propagandist of the national goals and interests of the Kazakh people.

The newspaper "Qazaq Tili" has made a significant contribution to raising the issues of socio-political, literary, cultural, socio-economic life of the Kazakh people.

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